

Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

D2.5 – Conceptual model and reference architecture II

WP2 Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User
Scenarios in iHelp

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Executive summary

iHelp aims to early detect and mitigate the risks associated with Pancreatic Cancer applying advanced Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based techniques to support the actors of the system. Those techniques are performed on historic data of cancer patients gathered from existing cohorts and biobanks. The models developed through the AI-based learning techniques will be useful to identify the risk earlier, and to elaborate a mitigation plan.

To this end, iHelp will use and extend the paradigm of Holistic Health Records (HHR) (K., A., B., + 17), in order to aggregate and re-use data needed by the Artificial Intelligence for developing their models. Several different sources will feed the common shared informative base, and for achieving this goal, a framework for the data ingestion will be provided for the pre-elaboration of different data in order to let it flow towards the shared data model.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide the consortium with a common high-level view about the whole solution. The details of each software artefact are delegated to the respective leader and will be described in the related deliverables.

During the period from M9 to M18, the consortium had several virtual and hybrid meetings to collect information and to agree about a common architecture. After the first released architecture in M8, thanks to the improved knowledge of the technical partners, and the details provided, some refinements were made.

The common agreement was reached about the general view, the platform will be constituted by containerised services, both from the data ingestion and the data analysis, with slight differences explained in this document.

The input of this deliverable was the D2.3 (“State of the art and Requirements Analysis III”) (M., A., C., + 22), that was analysed, and from which the needed components and interactions are identified and updated accordingly during this period.

This deliverable is being released at M18 of the project, and it will be useful for the D2.7 (“Functional and Non-Functional specifications II”) for defining its purpose, and to all the technical partners as reference architecture for the whole iHelp solution.

This is the final release of the architecture overview document for the iHelp project.

1 Introduction

The purpose of this document is to provide the final architecture that will drive the interactions among the different software artefacts developed by the iHelp partners. It will also be a basis for the components' names and will offer an analysis of the possible deployments.

The main purpose of this document is to define some guidelines within the consortium and to share a common view about the whole platform. The main topics that this document addresses concern the kind of software artefacts that will be developed, the communication pattern used, the kind of graphical user interface provided, the infrastructure needed for testing and validation, and the envisaged deployment.

This design document is the product of the work carried out by the task T2.2 ("Reference Architecture Specifications"). Main goal of that task is to analyse the requirements and to mediate with the technical partners to reach an agreement on which to design a reference architecture able to satisfy the requirements presents in D2.3 ("State of the art and requirements analysis III") (M., A., C., + 22). All the components' leaders were involved in the definition, refinement, and agreement on this common reference architecture.

This task ends in M20 and this document depicts the final agreement on the overall architecture of the iHelp platform.

This document does not address the internal choices regarding the design of the components, or the different nature of the data to be ingested or analysed, but it aims to clarify the impact of the gathered requirements onto the designed components and to highlight and describe some useful interactions.

The organisation structure of the document is the following:

- **Section 2** provides a global overview on the adopted architecture definition approach;
- **Section 3** aims to describe, both for technical and non-technical audience, how iHelp fits into the existing environments, who and how will use the system;
- **Section 4** is focused to describe what the main functionalities of the system are;
- **Section 5** recalls the principles and the assumptions made about security and privacy aspects;
- **Section 6** collects the envisaged software artefacts that will compose the iHelp solution;
- **Section 7** due to the heterogeneous nature of the pilot partners, this section depicts the infrastructure needed by iHelp in order to perform its tasks and provide its features;
- **Section 8** based on the infrastructure identified in the previous section, this section maps the component envisaged on the identified infrastructure for the actual deployment.

To better highlight the sections of this document that have been updated with respect to the first release, was added **Section 1.1**, in which are listed the updated parts of the document and briefly the impacted content impacted.

1.1 Updated Sections

3 - Context: Actors edited

4 - Functional Overview: New use cases

6.2.3 - Social Analyser: Objective and description of the component

6.4.1 - Analytic Workbench: Objective and description of the component

6.4.5 - Monitoring and Alerting: Objective and description of the component

6.3.7 - Secondary Data Pre-processor: Objective and description of the component

6.4.4 - Personalised Advisor: Objective and description of the component

6.2.1 - DSS Dashboard: Structure, objective and description of the component

6.3.1 - HHR Importer: Structure, objective and description of the component

6.3.6 - Data Capture Gateway: Structure, objective and description of the component

6.5.1 - Big Data Platform: Structure, objective and description of the component

6.5.2 - iHelp Store Rest: Structure, objective and description of this new component

6.4.2 - Personalised Predictor: Structure, objective and description of the component

6.4.3 - Predictor and Risk identifier: Structure, objective and description of the component

7 - Infrastructure: Details about the technologies and the component leader's workflow for deployment

8 - Deployment: New details and analysis result after the completion of the final phase of requirements elicitation.

2 Approach to the architecture definition

The main goal of the reference architecture of iHelp is to design a limited and well-defined set of component functionalities satisfying the user requirements scheduled for the first period of the project.

The architecture described in this document is the final release and any other needed improvement at the internal design of the components will be taken over by the component leaders. The adopted methodology and techniques guarantee a good level of confidence in the architectural choices made so far.

The approach adopted to describe the iHelp top-level architecture is based on existing literature (B. 13) and on previous experiences in other EU projects (CrowdHEALTH 22) (Markos 21) (SkinCancer 21) (PATHway 21).

The architecture described here has the following objectives:

- It serves as the blueprint both for the system and the project developing it;
- It defines the work assignments, in terms of component functionalities, that must be carried out by separate design and implementation teams;
- It is a vehicle for early analysis to make sure that the design approach will yield an acceptable system;
- It is the artefact that holds the key to post-deployment system understanding and/or mining efforts.

The definition of the iHelp architecture follows some goodness principles proposed in the scope of the NEXOF-RA project (NEXOF-RA project 08), which represents a quality model for the architectural design of software systems. The main quality attributes, considered in evaluating the alternative architectural choices, are the efficiency and the buildability (i.e. ease of realisation). This means that when multiple architectural alternatives were analysed, the solution considered most efficient and, in order of priority, the easiest to realise has been adopted. The most *efficient* solution for each component is the one that minimizes: (i) the time requested to perform its tasks; (ii) the amount of disk space requested to store internal data enabling its normal operation; and (iii) the overhead of communication with other components to exchange requested and provided data. When the simultaneous minimization of these three parameters has been not possible because of conflicting conditions, 'the best' trade-off among them has been chosen. The criteria to define the best trade-off assigns the highest priority to the minimization of the execution time requested to perform the tasks, secondly to the minimization of the overhead of communication with other components, and finally to the minimization of the amount of disk space required.

Accordingly, when high hardware requirements were expected, like CPU throughput and/or amount of memory, then it was decided to adopt a dedicated server in order to minimize the execution time even if such a choice does not optimize the efficiency in terms of communication overhead among distinct components. For the components designed to be replicable, in case of high load, the dynamic horizontal scaling has to be taken in account (i.e. for the Ingestion Pipeline Components §6.3). Naturally, when possible, it was agreed to have more components running on the same server and in the same execution environment (e.g. virtual machine, Kubernetes node) so to try to improve the communication as well (e.g. Data analysis components §6.4).

Other quality attributes have been taken in consideration, like the *modifiability* of the system, which is one of the most important quality attributes considered during the design. Indeed, the adopted incremental approach[9] implies continuous changes to the architecture and a highly modifiable system is strongly recommended. According to the adopted quality model, the modifiability is a complex attribute measured in terms of *extensibility* of capabilities, i.e. the ability to add new functionalities with less impact on the overall system, the deletion of unwanted capabilities, the *portability*, i.e. the ability of the system to run under different executing environment and the *restructuring*, i.e. the ability to support architectural configuration changes, such as rationalising system services, modularising, optimising or creating reusable components.

The *reusability* of some of the main components is a highly desired aspect for iHelp, even if it is not mandatory. Thus, one secondary goal of the iHelp architecture is to reduce as much as possible the coupling between components/micro-services, while keeping each component as cohesive as possible. The reusability of the components is an aspect that will be further investigated during the next steps of the project.

The possible constraints of the infrastructure that will host the iHelp trial platform have been tentatively evaluated in terms of the number of required servers and, for each of them, the amount of the required computational resources and disk space. Moreover, the technologies needed for the correct operation of the components have been considered; they are reported in Figure 19: Identified tools. The objective of such investigation is to verify the feasibility of the demonstrator and to gather any technical requirements from the infrastructure providers (i.e. the pilots' infrastructure for the on-premises deployments). The result of such investigation led to a gross grained estimation of the hardware requirements to execute iHelp components, provided by the component owners and submitted to the infrastructure provider for an acceptance validation. The estimated infrastructure requirements are reported in §7 and in the Annex A - Infrastructure Discussion.

The whole design phase, instead of focusing on specific tool/language and techniques used by the development teams, or micro-managing the internal architecture of the components/micro-services, concentrates on the protocols and interactions between the various software artefacts and on the health and usefulness of the system as a whole.

3 Context

In the iHelp project, a software platform will be developed and will provide several features, interacting with different actors. From the first version of deliverable D2.3 (“State of the art and requirements analysis III”) (M., A., C., + 22) these kinds of actors emerged:

- **Health Care Professional (HCP):** the physicians that will take care of the citizens’ health and risk of developing the Pancreatic Cancer
- **Individual:** the citizen or patient that will be enrolled in the iHelp project and that can access its functionalities
- **Model Builder:** the data scientist that can train the models for better tuning the evaluation algorithms of the AI
- **External Sources:** other external system, such as: laboratories, social networks, data bases, etc.
- **Policy Maker:** person in charge to making and implementing decision to improve the health and well-being of the public, scanning social media and analysing trends related to eHealth and pancreatic cancer.
- **Admin:** a technical profile that can interact with the components of the system, also using programmatic interfaces.

Figure 1: Actors of the system

The actors highlighted in dark orange, represent the new actors added during the second phase of this task.

The details of the target users and *personas* envisaged and analysed will be detailed in the scope of the deliverable produced by the T2.4 (“User centred design”).

The following diagram (Figure 2) places the actors in the context of the iHelp platform; the diagram will be drilled down in section (§1).

Figure 2: Context diagram

The big iHelp box, in the middle of Figure 2, abstracts all the complexity of the platform, that will include: the ability of the system to accept and transform data from external sources to the common data model; the components that implement the AI of the system; the services that provide the presentation layer for rendering the final user applications, the components that will manage the authentication, infrastructure components, and so on. All those main components will be detailed in the following sections.

4 Functional Overview

Starting from deliverable D2.3 (“State of the art and requirements analysis III”) (M., A., C., + 22) it is possible to enumerate the main use cases that drove the design phase; following their label with a short description of the envisaged behaviours. All details and specific interaction steps will be detailed in the scope of the task T2.3 (“Functional and Non-Functional specifications”).

In the following diagram, the use cases added during the second phase of this task are highlighted in dark orange.

Figure 3: Diagram of Use Cases - individual

Individual use cases:

- **Develop Risk Prediction Model:** allows the **ModelBuilder** to develop the prediction model
- **Risk Assessment:** allows the **HCP** to perform/trigger a risk assessment for a specific patient
- **Request Tests and Samples:** allows the **HCP** to generate a list of Tests that the patient has to perform
- **Elevated Risk Detected:** highlights to the **HCP** that an elevated risk of PC development was detected
- **Ingest Tests and Samples results:** allows the ingestion of data coming from a pilot laboratory test
- **Risk Mitigation/Treatment planning:** allows the **HCP** to plan a list of task(s) or goals to achieve, to be communicated to the patients in order to mitigate or treat the exacerbation of PC
- **Advice Review:** allows the **HCP** to endorse the suggestion proposed by the AI and allow the actual sending of the content
- **Risk Mitigation Delivery:** provides delivery of messages for the mitigation plan
- **Monitoring:** allows the automatic monitoring of patient shared data, in order to estimate if their behaviour is in line with the mitigation plan

- **Advice Follow-up:** allows the **HCP** to look at the progress of the mitigation plan
- **Caption of profiling characteristics:** allows the **HCP** to input relevant patients' characteristics into the platform
- **Reporting:** shows to the **HCP** patients data in form of an aggregate and elaborate report
- **Plan a visit or a remote contact:** allows the **HCP** to send a message, regarding a visit, to the patient using the iHelp platform
- **Data Visualisation:** is a view of the data present in the project storage
- **Communication of risk:** allows to communicate to the patient the computed risk of developing PC
- **[NEW] Social network data extraction:** allows the policymaker to understand the lifestyle trends and patterns on specific topics, to provide an impression of public sentiment which may help in developing new policies
- **[NEW] Patient enrolment using DSS Dashboard:** allows the **HCP** to enrol the patient into the iHelp platform, specifying all the available IDs currently present for the patient (e.g. Pilot internal ID and Healthentia ID) if known. That use case set the system to refer to the patient data using one of the provided IDs
- **[NEW] Patient enrolment using Healthentia:** allows the **Patient** to register himself into the iHelp platform, specifying all the available IDS currently present for him/her (e.g. iHelp ID and Pilot internal ID) if known. That use case set the system to refer to the patient data using one of the provided IDs

In the following Figure 4, are depicted the use cases related to the **Admin** actors. Due to the technical nature of those use cases, detailing them is not in the scope of this document. During the present task, the purpose was to highlight that those use cases were needed for configuring the system properly. Still, after analysing those use cases in detail, it emerged that the admin interacts with just one software artefact at a time, so we left the detail of those functionalities to every component leader.

Figure 4: Diagram of Use Cases - Admin

Admin use cases:

- **[NEW] Connectors configuration:** allows the **DataManager** to configure the connectors for the specific external service
- **[NEW] Manually data input:** allows the **DataManager**, if needed, to insert the Primary/Secondary data manually through an API
- **[NEW] Manage Users:** allows the **IdentityManager**, interacting with the IAM of the project, to add, remove or edit the users and their details
- **[NEW] Manage Security Policies:** allows the **IdentityManager**, interacting with the IAM of the project, to set the security policy to be used in the iHelp project
- **[NEW] Manage Privacy Policies:** allows the **IdentityManager**, interacting with the IAM of the project, to set the privacy policy to be used in the iHelp project
- **[NEW] Monitoring rules configuration:** allows the **DataManager**, to set the details and properties of the rule engine provided by the **Monitoring and Alerting component**
- **[NEW] Study Setup:** allows the **DataManager**, to set detail of the pilot's study, interacting directly with the cockpit provided by the **Secondary Data Pre-processor**

From deliverable D2.3 (“State of the art and requirements analysis III”) (M., A., C., + 22) and analysing this list of use cases, it is clear that the iHelp platform aims to support both clinicians and patients. The overview of the principal function produced a list of common requirements, that also impact the overall architecture.

The first need, clear for all pilots, is the capability of the platform to ingest data, coming from different sources. Those data, managed following the ethics principles described in deliverable D1.10 (“Ethical Issues Related to the Protection of Personal Data”) (M., M. 21) are accepted, formatted, cleaned, mapped and transformed in a common data model; this pipeline will be better detailed in the scope of the WP3.

Those uniformed data are stored inside the iHelp storage repository, a big data platform, for further queries; the WP4 is taking care of this process.

The data that come into the repository, can also come from the **Individual**, through a mobile application and its dedicated backend. Those data will feed the repository as well, through the same ingestion pipeline.

A **ModelBuilder**, using its dedicated GUI, will train the AI algorithms on the data present in the repository, that will support the **HCPs** in their job.

The same data will be accessed by all the components that provide the AI algorithms, analyses and aggregations that will be shown to the **HCP**; those components, model and algorithms will be taken care of in the scope of WP4 and WP5.

5 Security and Privacy

The system shall be compliant with the security and privacy requirements expressed in the deliverable D2.3 (“State of the art and requirements analysis III”) (M., A., C., + 22), and all the components are responsible to comply with the Privacy-By-Design and Privacy-By-Default principles presents in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (TEPatcotEU. 21) and any other privacy constraint that could emerge from the use cases.

The GDPR is a regulation in EU law on data protection and privacy for all individuals within the European Union (EU) and the European Economic Area (EEA). It also addresses the export of personal data outside the EU and EEA areas. The GDPR aims primarily to give control to individuals over their personal data and to simplify the regulatory environment for international business by unifying the regulation within the EU. Superseding the Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC, the regulation contains provisions and requirements pertaining to the processing of personal data of individuals inside the EEA and applies to any company established in the EEA or – regardless of its location and the data subjects’ citizenship—that is processing the personal information of data subjects inside the EEA.

The GDPR will apply when there is a “processing” of personal data. The activities that are considered to constitute a ‘processing’ have not gone through any significant change within the GDPR, which maintains a very broad scope of application.

Accordingly, the GDPR will apply in case of “any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction”.

It goes without saying that iHelp involves processing of personal data within the meaning of the GDPR. Hence, the various principles and obligations set therein will need to be carefully assessed and complied with by the stakeholders involved.

The data protection principles are at the core of the processing of personal data. Many of them already existed under the Data Protection Directive and are now reinforced in the GDPR. Article 5(1) of the GDPR lists the key principles relating to the processing of personal data (examined in the following six sub-Sections). Article 5(2) provides for a general principle of “accountability”, according to which the controller¹ shall be responsible for, and able to demonstrate compliance with, the other six principles.

¹ The data controller determines the purposes for which and the means by which personal data is processed. The data processor processes personal data only on behalf of the controller (European Commission 22).

Figure 5: Overview of data protection principles

- **Lawfulness, fairness & transparency**
 - personal data must be processed lawfully, fairly, and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject. The latter “transparency” requirement supplements what already existed in the Data Protection Directive.
- **Purpose limitation**
 - personal data must be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes; and must not be further processed in a way incompatible with those purposes
- **Data minimisation**
 - personal data must be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed. Also, the period for which the data are stored should be limited to a strict minimum. Finally, personal data should only be processed if the purpose of the processing cannot be fulfilled by other means
- **Accuracy**
 - personal data must be accurate and, where necessary, kept up-to-date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that inaccurate personal data, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay
- **Storage limitation**
 - personal data must be kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed. Personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as the data will be processed solely

for archiving purposes in the public interest, or scientific and historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 83(1) and subject to implementation of appropriate technical and organisational measures

- **Integrity and confidentiality**
 - personal data must be processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures.
- **Data governance and accountability:** the principle of accountability, which essentially refers to the various obligations organisations will have to follow in order to demonstrate compliance with data protection requirements, is not a new concept but is now expressly included in Article 5(2) of the GDPR. Hence, with the adoption of the GDPR, it now plays a significant role in the EU privacy regulatory framework

One of the ways to demonstrate accountability is through adopting the “**Privacy by design**” measures. This entails that every component or software artefact must implement appropriate technical and organisational measures (e.g. pseudonymisation techniques) designed to implement the data protection principles (e.g. data minimisation). Said measures must be implemented in an effective way so as to integrate the necessary safeguards into the data processing in order to meet the requirements of the GDPR and to protect the rights of data subjects. Said obligations must be respected both at the time of the determination of the means for processing and at the time of the processing itself. Some elements to consider while implementing the measures are: (i) the state of the art; (ii) the cost of implementation; (iii) the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing; and (iv) the risks of varying likelihood and severity for rights and freedoms of individuals posed by the processing.

The privacy by design requirement should be carefully assessed by both the developers and the pilots (when initially collecting and processing personal data). The pilots must consider the implementation of appropriate technical and organisational measures in order to comply with the privacy by design requirement. As for the solution as such, it is recommended to carefully consider the privacy by design requirements in order to protect privacy by embedding it into the design specifications. This is done in particular through the application of pseudonymisation and anonymisation techniques. More detailed aspects were addressed in the context of WP1 and reported in the deliverables about the ethical issues and data management plan (M., M. 21) (F. 21) (F., K., A. 21) (M., M., M., + 21) (M., A., C., + 21).

6 Software Architecture

In this section the main components that constitute the iHelp platform will be detailed, implementing the requirements emerged in the deliverable D2.3 (“State of the art and requirements analysis III”) (M., A., C., + 22).

A simple overview of the platform is shown in Figure 6 in which are visible four big blocks as a placeholder for the more detailed description below.

The **Final user applications** are the apps (either mobile or web) that are dedicated to the human actors of the system (i.e., **HCP**, **Individual**, **ModelBuilder** and **Policy Makers**).

The **Data Ingestion** represents all those components that are able to process data derived from different sources, also external to the iHelp project, and that can handle data in order to store them, compliant with the common data model, into the central **Data Storage**.

Symmetrically, the **Data Analysis** and **Additional Features** blocks, abstract from the AI and monitoring components that elaborates the data present in the **Data Storage** for feeding the **Final User Applications**.

Figure 6: Simple Overview

6.1 Overall

In Figure 7 we can see a more detailed diagram of the overall architecture of the iHelp platform.

A standard modelling language was not adopted for this kind of diagram, for better explaining also to the non-technical partners the connections and the dependencies among components.

In particular, the shape of the software artefact mainly brings the concept of communication pattern, while a hexagon denotes the micro-services that communicate asynchronously, using a message broker and a rectangle defines the components that offer or use an API for asynchronous communication.

Different types of lines, solid and dashed, were used to identify different communication protocols among components (e.g., **REST**, **JDBC**, **HTTP**, etc.). The direction of the arrows graphically simplifies the lollipop notation derived from UML v2.0 (OMG 21) and used in the first version of this deliverable; nonetheless the semantic remains the same, the direction of the arrows depicts that the component (or set of components) touched by the head of the arrow, will provide the interface that is used by the component (or set of components) put at the beginning of the arrow.

Other than the functional components, in the diagram some infrastructural components are also shown, needed for enabling the execution of the solution.

Generically, in microservice architectures, the UI usually connects with multiple microservices. If the microservices are finely grained, the client(s) may need to connect with lots of microservices, which becomes challenging. Also, the services, including their APIs, can evolve.

One possible way to solve these issues is to use **API Gateway**. API Gateway sits between the final user applications and the iHelp platform and acts as a façade. It can work as a reverse proxy, routing the client request to the appropriate service. It can also support the client request's fanning-out to multiple microservices and then return the aggregated responses to the client. It additionally supports essential cross-cutting concerns (such as authentication, load balancing, dependency resolution, data transformations and dynamic request dispatching can be handled in a convenient and generic way). In the iHelp reference architecture the block labelled **API Gateway**, will dispatch the external invocation to specific internal services; the consortium agreed with the adoption of **Traefik** tool (TraefikLabs 22).

In order to allow access only to authorised users, the iHelp solution will adopt an internal **IdentityManger**, based on the open source product **Keycloak** (Keycloak 22), that will take care of the resources access. iHelp can be configured to support OpenID Connect. OpenID Connect (OIDC) (OpenId 22) is an authentication protocol that is an extension of Oauth 2.0. While Oauth 2.0 is only a framework for building authorization protocols and is mainly incomplete, OIDC is a full-fledged authentication and authorization protocol. OIDC also makes heavy use of the Json Web Token (JWT) set of standards. These standards define an identity token JSON format and ways to digitally sign and encrypt that data in a compact and web-friendly way.

About the internal communication, the possible choices were mainly split into two main different branches, synchronous or asynchronous communication. Although synchronous communication is not a problem in a monolithic application, due to the simple context (i.e. a client sends a request and waits for a response), in a scenario where multiple services call each other in a non-trivial way, this can produce a waterfall of failing calls. For this reason, and for the sake of flexibility toward any further change or improvement of the requests flow, for the envisaged high demanding process an asynchronous communication pattern was designed for the envisaged high demanding process.

Specifically, the constituent components of the data ingestion building block communicate through a message broker. Nevertheless, to decentralise the coordination, instead of a static orchestration, a choreography transaction was designed, specifically applied to the SAGA pattern for transactions. Thanks

to this choice, each software artefact has a “brain” that can decide, listening to all the other components, if an action should be taken or not. This approach simplifies the possible refinement of the pipeline without impacting the single development of each single component by different teams. The specific flow and the detailed interactions will be explained better in the scope of WP3.

Available for all the components, but specifically used inside the pipeline ingestion, iHelp will also use Apache **Kafka** (Apache 22), a message broker and stream processor which allows to publish, subscribe, archive and process streams of records in real time. It is designed to manage data streams from multiple sources by distributing them to multiple consumers.

Apart from the decision to use Kafka as the platform’s message broker mechanism, regarding the devOps, the iHelp consortium agreed with the adoption of **Kubernetes** (Kubernetes 22). Kubernetes (k8s) is an open source platform that automates Linux container operations. It eliminates many of the manual processes involved in deploying and scaling containerized applications and allows to manage host clusters running containers easily and efficiently.

Figure 7: Overall Architecture

The goal and the main envisaged interactions of the components are described below.

6.2 Final User applications

6.2.1 DSS Dashboard

6.2.1.1 Objective of the software artefact

The Decision Support system will allow physicians and policy makers to analyse data and make decisions for both individuals and groups of patients. The DSS will be able to analyse data from a relational database through the execution of SQL statements and also to design more complex analytics through workflows. The **DSS dashboard** will provide visualization capabilities to present the analytics results. Different types of users will be considered, from data scientists who will define the analytics and their visualization, to nurses that may monitor a patient data.

6.2.1.2 Interactions with other components

Expected interfaces

The DSS interacts with databases and executes analytics on different types of data. The DSS needs REST APIs to interact with data stores and the different analytical models.

Offered Interfaces

The DSS will provide different interfaces for data scientist and physicians to log into the system, create federated queries and analytic workflows, and display the results from federated queries and analytics on different types of charts and dashboards.

Figure 8 shows an example of the login interface to access the different functionalities of the DSS.

Figure 8: Login interface

Figure 9 shows an example of a dashboard that displays the rows of a table from a database selected from the *Database* drop-down menu. The first 50 rows stored in the selected table are displayed at the bottom of the figure.

Figure 9: Database’s data visualization

Figure 10 and Figure 11 depict two different dashboards where data returned from SQL queries is visualized. Figure 10 shows patient data as text fields and as a bar chart. Figure 11 shows the results as a pie chart, horizontal bar chart, radar chart, and lines chart.

Figure 10: Individual patient data visualization

Figure 11: Different chart types

Figure 12 shows an example workflow where the data scientist creates federated queries and analytic workflows and defines the associated dashboards.

Figure 12: Workflow UI

Different sets of nodes will be created to interact with the iHelp storage, the iHelp Analytic Workflow, the iHelp personalized predictor and iHelp predictor and risk identifier components. Figure 13: Developed set of nodes to be used in the Workflow UI to interact with other iHelp components, shows the created set of nodes that allows to interact with the iHelp storage, the iHelp Analytic Workflow, the iHelp personalized predictor developed at this moment.

Figure 13: Developed set of nodes to be used in the Workflow UI to interact with other iHelp components

Technological stack requirements

The DSS will use a core technology Node-Red (OpenJs Foundation 22), a flow-based development tool that allows creating programs by dragging and dropping different nodes and connecting the nodes to create the expected code flow. Python libraries for analytics like Pandas for data analysis and scikit-learn, Theano and TensorFlow for machine learning purposes may be included in the DSS.

6.2.2 Mobile App

6.2.2.1 Objective of the software artefact

The **Mobile App** component is the main user interface for patients/citizens in the various iHelp Pilots. As the name suggests, this component is a mobile application that is available for download from the Google Play Store² (for Android users) and the Apple App Store³ (for iOS users). The application (Healthentia) is already available for download (see links in footnotes).

The Healthentia application is an app that can be used in various trial/study configurations, so the exact functionality of the mobile app depends on the user who is logged into the application, and the trial/study in which he/she participates. The type of functionalities offered by the mobile app in iHelp can broadly be described as:

- Monitor the user’s lifestyle and symptoms through connected sensors, self-reported events and answering questionnaires from within the app.
- Communicate with the patient’s/citizen’s healthcare professional, either through messages, teleconferencing, or by receiving notifications directly from the professional.
- Provide virtual coaching to the patient/citizen – offering health education, advice, through visualisations of measured data, simple feedback messages or in-depth conversations with a digital virtual coach.

The main objective for this component is to design and develop the functionalities needed to support up to 5 different application configurations linked to the 5 iHelp Pilots. It may be possible to use the same application configuration for 2 different pilots, or it may be necessary to have 5 different configurations – this will depend on the details of the pilots as they are being specified. Details of the exact design and development progress of the mobile application may be found in D5.6 (“Delivery mechanisms for personalised healthcare and real-time feedback I”) submitted on M16 and in D5.7 (“Delivery mechanisms for personalised healthcare and real-time feedback II”) that is planned to be submitted on M32.

As background technology, the existing Healthentia application supports a number of functionalities mostly related to monitoring patients/citizens, as listed here:

- Questionnaires – A set of questions with various supported types (e.g., multiple choice, Visual Analogue Scales, Likert Scale) that are triggered to be answered by the user at defined time intervals.
- Physical Activity Monitoring – By connecting an external tracking device, the application can monitor the user’s daily levels of physical activity.
- Sleep Monitoring – By connecting external tracking devices that support tracking sleep, the application can monitor the user’s daily sleep patterns.
- Liquid Intake – Through self-reporting, the application allows the user to measure their own liquid intake during the day.
- Symptom and Event Reporting – Through self-reporting, the application allows the user to report any number of predefined events or health related symptoms.

² <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.innovationsprint.healthentia&hl=en&gl=US>

³ <https://apps.apple.com/nl/app/healthentia/id1491757656?l=en#?platform=iphone>

In order to satisfy the core objectives of the Mobile App component in supporting the various iHelp Pilots, the focus will be on adding various types of functionality related to providing feedback and coaching to the end-users, as further defined in D2.1 (“State of the art and requirements analysis I”).

6.2.2.2 Interactions with other components

The iHelp **Mobile App** component is a series of configurations of the Healthentia Mobile App which is embedded into the Healthentia platform. From a technical perspective, the mobile app is a client to the Healthentia platform, which means that it is the only component it directly communicates to. In Figure 14 below, we depict the iHelp Mobile App and its direct interactions with the Healthentia **Data Service** and the Healthentia **Virtual Coach Service**. The connections with the Data Service are mostly already in place, and are used to support the monitoring functionalities of the application (e.g. retrieving data from external tracking devices, or storing questionnaire data). The connections with the Virtual Coach Service are to be implemented in the iHelp project, and support the delivery of feedback and personalized healthcare from other iHelp components (e.g. the – Personalised Advisor see §6.4.4).

In summary, there are three types of interactions with the mobile app:

- The end-user that will use the **Mobile App** as their primary GUI.
- The data services that enable collection of data through the app (see §6.3.7 – Secondary Data Pre-processor).
- The coaching services that enable the delivery of personalized feedback and coaching (see §6.4.4 – Personalised Advisor).

Figure 14: iHelp Mobile App and its direct interactions with other components

The mobile app collects data (Reports and Questionnaires) which is stored in the Data Service. At the same time, the app visualizes data from 3rd party sensor providers (e.g., Garmin, Fitbit) through the same Data Service. The digital virtual coach is powered by a separate service (Virtual Coach Service), which in turn is controlled via through the iHelp Personalised Advisor.

6.2.3 Social Analyser

6.2.3.1 Objective of the software artefact

The **Social Analyser** component is responsible for the analysis of discussion taking place on the social media platforms in order to provide insight into the lifestyle trends, mental models, emotions, social interactions and societal influences on the individuals who either have developed the Cancer or are in the early stage of risk identification. This type of information about social aspects is important to analyse/evaluate the impact of the risks, the personalised healthcare and/or the targeted recommendations by the clinical experts.

The **Social Analyser** component will use Complex Event Processing (CEP) techniques, in addition to the state-of-the art Natural Language Processing (NLP), Sentiment Network Analysis (SNA) and AI technologies to provide a complete toolkit for clinicians and policy makers; allowing them to collect, process and visualize Cancer related information exchanged on the social media platforms. In this respect, the objectives of the Social Analyser component (as described in the iHelp DoA are) are:

- To develop mechanisms for real-time analysis of social data and contribution to policy making activities
- To define mechanisms for efficient monitoring, alerts and feedback gathering regarding the personalised recommendations and user-centric healthcare solutions developed in the project
- To evaluate the benefits of AI and personalised healthcare approach developed in the project

In addition to the above, the following objectives are defined for the **Social Analyser** component:

- To extract iHelp relevant information (e.g. discussions on risk identification, targeted recommendations, etc.) from social media discussions and present it to policy makers in an easy to interpret and easy to understand way
- To integrate the analysis of social media data with the iHelp **Big Data Platform**
- To present the social media analysis in such a way that policy makers will be able to analyse the general healthcare trends as well as impact of specific recommendations/policies

The outcome of the Social Analyser engine will be presented to the relevant decision makers as the feedback loop to the clinicians/policy makers, allowing them to make more informed decisions regarding targeted recommendations and policies

The **Social Analyser** component will utilise a number of sub-components, each with a specific purpose that contributes towards delivering a comprehensive social media analysis and decision support system. The following sub-components are used by the Social Analyser:

- **CEP Engine** to develop event patterns and event trends based on expert and machine learning methodologies. The engine will be extended to enable the inference of probabilistic events suitable for early risk identification and evaluation of targeted recommendations.
- **NLP** to analyse, decipher, understand and make sense of the human languages in a manner that is useful for the objectives of the Social Analyser component
- **SNA** to analyse social networks on the social media platforms and to extract relevant information about the structure of the networks, identify clusters or communities and predict new links between users
- **Administrative Dashboard** to create alerts by specifying which topics (keywords and phrases) they are interested in monitoring on specific social media platforms. These topics can relate to the lifestyle trends, mental models, emotional intelligence, social interactions and societal influences on the individuals
- **Monitoring Dashboard** to provide real-time monitoring updates on the pre-specified alerts through a set of intuitive visualisations. The alerts will show e.g., how many social media posts are being posted on specific topic(s), from whom, when and the pattern of posts
- **Clickhouse** is an open-source relational database management system (RDBMS). It organizes data into one or more data tables in which data types may be related to each other. It is used to store data about users of the social media analysis solution
- **Apache Kafka** is a system to manage the events' logs. It is a durable messaging system that sends messages between processes, applications, and servers. Apache Kafka is used as a message brokering system in the social media analysis component. It is where the messages will be published for processing by different components in the social media analysis solution

- **Apache ZooKeeper** is a centralized service for maintaining configuration information, naming, providing distributed synchronization, and providing group services. ZooKeeper is used to coordinate and manage different components in the social media analysis solution

6.2.3.2 Interactions with other components

The **Social Analyser** component will provide intuitive interfaces (as Administrative and Monitoring Dashboards) to the users, which are perceived to be clinicians and other healthcare related policymakers. The component doesn't require input from any other component within the iHelp platform as it gets input directly from the users (i.e., alerts on specific topics) and social media platforms (i.e., data concerning discussions taking place related to the alert-topics).

Figure 15: Overview of the Social Analysis component

However, the output of the Social Analyser component will be stored in the iHelp platform e.g., as additional data type in the HHR structure. In this respect, the **Social Analyser** will interact with the following component in the iHelp platform:

Data Capture Gateway – to ingest the social analytic data within the **Big data Platform**

6.3 Data Ingestion

6.3.1 HHR Importer

6.3.1.1 Objective of the software artefact

The objective of the **HHR Importer** is to store data received under in the HHR format into the **Big Data Platform** component of the iHelp platform. During the ingestion process, raw (primary) and aggregated (secondary) data are mapped and transformed to the common HHR model. At the final stage of the data ingestion pipeline, the HHR importer takes the transformed data and persistently stores them in the datastore. The latter has defined a relational schema that is compatible with the E-R conceptual model of HHR and this software artefact will implement the following two functionalities:

- Transform the HHR entities to various data items that will be stored into data tables of the Big Data Platform.
- Establish the data connectivity with the datastore and perform all relevant operations in order to persistently store the produced data items. This will make use of the Kafka connector that allows to transparently store data from a Kafka topic to the **Big Data Platform**, exploiting the capabilities of the latter for data ingestion at very high rates.

The functionality of this component will be packaged as a Java archive and will be deployed as a static standalone microservice. At the final phase of the project, we will study the possibility to allow the dynamic deployment of this functionality upon request of the data provider to ingest his or her dataset.

6.3.1.2 Interactions with other components

This component interacts with the other software artefacts involved in the data ingestion pipeline and the **Big Data Platform** via **Kafka** data queues. It will provide an interface that will allow any other software artefact to push any HHR data compliant with the FHIR format. As a result, the component will be waiting for any other component to send data that need to be stored in the **Big Data Platform**. No GUI will be provided for this component. Its interface will not be exposed as a REST API, rather than:

- For static deployment, it will listen for new data arriving in a predefined Kafka topic in a HHR format
- For dynamic deployment, it will get all its configuration parameters (i.e. name of the Kafka topic to listen to) upon its initialization, and then do the same as in the static deployments

Those will allow other components to invoke it, or a much simpler interface will be provided to allow the serverless platform to pass meta-information parameters, such as data queue specific information. In case of the latter option, this information will be used internally to connect to a Kafka queue and data will be retrieved by the specified topic.

The HHR Importer does not produce any output data. The result of its invocation will be a transition of the state of the Big Data Platform. This transition is the result of a data modification operation (i.e. data insertion) that is successfully committed in the database layer. The **HHR importer** will interact with the **Big Data Platform** using one of its provided data connectors, the datastore's Kafka connector.

6.3.2 Data Gateway

6.3.2.1 Objective of the software artefact

The **Data Gateway** microservice exposes a REST API through which the iHelp connectors can send their data to the iHelp platform. The communication is done through HTTPS and the Data Gateway performs two main actions:

- Message authentication, where the Data Gateway checks the provided security keys in the message against the ones defined for a specific connector.
- Message transformation, where the message is sent to the Message Streaming Platform (Kafka) in the appropriate format.

6.3.2.2 Interactions with other components

The **Data Gateway** microservice is consumed by the iHelp Data connectors, that is, the connectors send the primary and secondary data that they gather to the Data Gateway, in order to initiate the ingestion pipeline. The **Data Gateway** transforms the REST request received to a Kafka message and relays the data to the next component without making any other transformations.

6.3.3 Data Harmoniser

6.3.3.1 Objective of the software artefact

Data Harmoniser will be utilized as an integrated microservice in the overall iHelp platform. It seeks to support and harmonise data coming from heterogeneous sources into a common format. To this end, its main aim is to provide annotated / correlated health data and harmonize them with the widely used HL7 FHIR format. The microservice will use its own internal sub-mechanism in order to correlate data resources

with HL7 FHIR resources to be compliant with the HHR model that will be defined in the scope of the task T3.1 (“Data Modelling and Integrated Health Records”).

The Primary Mapper sub-component will enable the mapping of primary data, that is the clinical data from the electronic health records, into the common data format that will be used in the iHelp platform (HHR). The component will provide the necessary transformation functions that are required to map the primary data to the holistic health records stored in the iHelp platform.

The Secondary Mapper sub-component will enable the mapping of secondary data (e.g. from mobile, wearable and social-media platforms) into the data format (schema, model) used in the iHelp platform (HHR). The component will provide necessary transformation functions that are required to map the secondary data from heterogeneous sources to the holistic health records stored in the iHelp platform. The Secondary Mapper will be an integral part of the iHelp platform as it supports the enrichment of typical health records with the secondary (e.g. lifestyle, social, etc.) data of the individuals.

6.3.3.2 Interactions with other components

The **Data Harmoniser** microservice will be utilized dynamically whenever it is selected, or when it is considered necessary and mandatory by the dataset provider. This microservice will be integrated with the provided message bus mechanism and it will consume and produce corresponding messages to this. The message to be consumed should be cleaned data, which will be further harmonised and transformed, hence an annotated, transformed and HL7 FHIR format aligned message will be the output of this specific microservice. To this end, the Data Harmoniser microservice has been determined to integrate closely with the **Data Cleaner** microservice.

In deeper details, the Data Harmoniser microservice incorporates the use of three (3) integrated sub-mechanisms, as also presented in the below figure (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Data Harmoniser

- **Semantic Analysis with NLP:** In this second sub mechanism translated data will be analysed, transformed, and annotated with appropriate metadata and controlled vocabularies will be identified and designed through the utilization of Semantic Web technologies coupled and enhanced by the utilization of NLP techniques, such as Named Entity Recognition (NER), Part-of-Speech Tagging etc.
- **Ontology & Structure Mapping:** This sub mechanism seeks to interlink annotated and transformed data with proper identified ontologies from the healthcare domain and in the HL7 FHIR format,

and to correlate datasets among them. Successful annotation, transformation and mapping of data and corresponding ontologies in terms of semantic and syntactic interoperability of data is one of the key elements of the Data Harmoniser mechanism.

6.3.4 Data Cleaner

6.3.4.1 Objective of the software artefact

Data Cleaner will be utilized as an integrated microservice in the overall iHelp project and its main objective is to deliver the software implementation that will provide the assurance that the provided data coming from several heterogeneous data sources will be clean and complete, to the extent possible. This microservice will be designed to minimize and filter the non-important data, thus improving the data quality and importance.

6.3.4.2 Interactions with other components

The **Data Cleaner** microservice will be utilized for every new incoming dataset in the platform since it seeks to detect and correct (or remove) inaccurate or corrupted data from the datasets. The input to this microservice will be provided by the shared message bus which will be utilized in the scopes of the iHelp project (e.g. Kafka). The topic from which data in the format of messages will be consumed can be set either dynamically, as a parameter whenever the microservice is called, or statically, based on an agreement in case that it is preferred. The input message will be the whole dataset in order to allow microservice to provide all the necessary cleaning actions towards the aim to produce consistent and cleaned data and datasets.

On top of this, the **Data Cleaner** service will be comprised of three (3) discrete, but integrated with each other, sub mechanisms which are listed below.

- **Data Validation:** This service will ensure that the other iHelp microservices will operate on clean, correct and useful data. Therefore, the Data Validation service will perform data validation of the incoming information data with the purpose of identifying errors based on conformance to a specific set of constraints.
- **Data Cleaning:** Entails the main sub mechanism of the Data Cleaner microservice. Its main goal is to correct or remove all the data elements for which validation errors were raised, considering missing, irregular, unnecessary, and inconsistent data. Thus, the Data Cleaning sub mechanism will perform the necessary corrections or removal of errors identified by the Data Validation Service.
- **Data Verification:** The main objective of this sub mechanism is to check the data elements of a dataset for accuracy and inconsistencies after the steps of data validation and cleaning are performed. To this end, it will ensure that all the corrective actions performed by the Data Cleaning service will be executed in compliance with the data models design of the iHelp platform. To this end, this service seeks to ensure that data will accurately be corrected or completed, and that the dataset will eventually be error free.

6.3.5 Data Qualifier

6.3.5.1 Objective of the software artefact

The scope of the **Data Qualifier** microservice is to automatically categorize both known and unknown data sources to specific “levels of trustfulness” (i.e. data reliability, provided data type, data source

availability) according to a given threshold, resulting into the adaptive selection of all the available reliable data sources in order to be connected into the iHelp project. To this end, this microservice seeks to provide a predictive selection mechanism for achieving data sources reliability during runtime and for providing the decision whether a connected data source will be considered as reliable or not as a result of the execution.

6.3.5.2 Interactions with other components

The **Data Qualifier** microservice will be utilized for every new registered data source and every incoming dataset in the platform because its goal is to enhance and adapt the selection of reliable sources. This specific microservice will also be integrated with the message bus mechanism provided in the scope of iHelp project. To this end, the whole dataset and information about the data source should be the input to this microservice in order to provide the reliability levels of the connected data sources into a message (i.e. String) format, which will be annotated to the dataset as metadata. This specific microservice has been identified to integrate with the **Data Cleaner** microservice in a dynamically modifiable workflow, since these two microservices may be utilized in different order depending on the type of data, sources, and the preferences of the data provider. The latter indicates that in terms of safeguarding the good quality of the incoming data and the reliability of the data sources, there may be the need in one scenario to utilize the **Data Cleaner** before the **Data Qualifier**, in order to provide cleaned data before the qualification of the dataset and the data, while in another scenario it is preferred to have at first the qualification of the data source and the dataset and then to perform the **Data Cleaner** microservice.

6.3.6 Data Capture Gateway

6.3.6.1 Objective of the software artefact

The objective of this type of software artefact (*known in the first version as Data connector*) is to allow connection with the data providers in order to retrieve data from the source and send it to the beginning of the data ingestion pipeline. There have been defined different types of data connectors, each one of those will provide different means for connectivity. So far, we have envisioned a connector that can get data stored in static files in an FTP server, another type of connector that can execute a query statement in a JDBC compatible database and an additional one that will provide a REST API to allow for secondary data to be pushed. However, the **Data Capture Gateway** is generic, thus allowing for other types of primary or secondary data connectors that might be needed during the progress of the project, without violating the principles and design of this component. It will be further investigated during the progress of the project if other types of primary data connectors will be required, such as listening to a specific topic of the **Kafka** broker that the social analyser might send its input.

For the configuration of the data ingestion, the **Data Capture Gateway** exposes a REST API that accepts the connector specific parameters, along with other information that needs to be taken into account by all involved data functions of the data ingestion pipeline. That is, the schema of the ingested data, potential cleaning rules etc. The REST API allows to submit a *job* for capturing data from an external source, monitor its progress or even schedule a *job* to be submitted in future or periodically. It also allows to define a *combo job* to be executed, which is a list of individual jobs that need to be executed in a specific order (i.e. there might be needed to firstly import a dataset containing information about the patients, and at a later phase a dataset that contains their medical treatments). A *scheduled combo job* can also be defined.

Each of the connectors will be released as Java archives and will be available to the **Data Gateway**, so that the latter can make use of the appropriate one to fetch data from the source and start ingesting it to the data pipeline.

6.3.6.2 Interactions with other components

This set of software artefacts interact with the **Data Gateway** and the external data sources, that can be of different types. According to its type, it can read data autonomously or allow for external components to periodically push data to the connector, or for the latter to pull data from the external sources. For instance, in case of a static or periodic data ingestion (batch ingestion) the component will read data from the external source, using the corresponding connector. In case of the secondary data ingestion, the corresponding component (i.e. the **Secondary Data Pre-processor**) will expose a REST API to allow the secondary data collector (i.e. a data connector) to periodically retrieve pre-processed secondary data and send those in a predefined format that needs to be further defined. In case of a streaming ingestion that might be needed, it will connect to a **Kafka** topic and continuously listen for incoming data.

Regarding input data, in case of a batch ingestion processing input data is the meta-information regarding the parameters that the corresponding connectors need to know in order to establish the data connectivity (i.e. URI of the ftp server and the path to read the data). In case of the secondary data ingestion, input data will be the aggregated data that the secondary data connector will send, in a format that will be defined in the forthcoming period of the project.

All primary data connectors will produce as output byte buffers that are generic and that enclose the data received, along with the type of the dataset. These connectors are dataset agnostic and therefore they treat all received information as byte buffers, as their purpose is only to establish the data connectivity, and not to perform any data processing. At a latter phase, it might be decided that the output of the primary data connectors can additionally send the schema definition of the dataset in the output. The output will be sent to the Data Gateway that will forward the byte stream to the corresponding Kafka topics that the functions involved in the data ingestion pipeline should listen to.

6.3.7 Secondary Data Pre-processor

6.3.7.1 Objective of the software artefact

The iHelp secondary data is about dynamic data arriving online from sensors or questionnaires, obtained outside a clinical setting, attempting to describe various aspects of everyday life. These aspects are expected to be physiological (exercise, nutrition, body signals), psychological, social and environmental, to be finalised at the requirements collection phase of T2.1 (“Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp”). The scope of the **Secondary Data Pre-processor** component is to collect this dynamic everyday-life raw data and process it into higher-level information.

Raw secondary data are objective measurements from IoT devices, or subjecting reports and self-assessments collected using the mobile application (see section 6.2.2). Devices will be integrated utilizing either APIs or SDKs from their manufacturers for automated measurements. In the API case (most probable), the integration will be carried out at the Secondary Data Pre-processor component, by interfacing with the device manufacturers’ servers. In the rarer case where an SDK is provided by the device manufacturer, the integration functionality of the component has to be moved into the mobile application

one. Questionnaires will be built in the mobile app. The Secondary Data Pre-processor component will be collecting all the patient data from the mobile application.

Raw secondary data are also to be processed to yield higher-level information including relationships, interactions, experiences, habits and behaviours that can influence people's health, design of preventative measures or risk of developing (chronic) conditions. To do so, signal processing and/or machine learning algorithms will be employed to capture secondary data semantics. These algorithms are also implemented in the Secondary Data Pre-processor component.

6.3.7.2 Interactions with other components

The **Secondary Data Pre-processor** component has two types of data input to autonomously get the raw patient secondary data:

- The interaction with the mobile application is done by offering an API to be used by the mobile application to push the available data.
- The interaction with the servers of the device manufactures is done via their API. The exact mode of interaction differs across device manufacturers, for example Fitbit provides endpoints to be called ad hoc to pull data, while Garmin allows the component to register itself and push new data, whenever available, to the server.

The **Secondary Data Pre-processor** component serves the raw and the processed higher-level secondary data to the iHelp platform by interfacing with the **Data Capture Gateway** component. To this aim it offers an API to receive requests for data originating from the Data Connectors component.

6.4 Data analysis

6.4.1 Analytic Workbench

6.4.1.1 Objective of the software artefact

The **Analytic Workbench** component in the iHelp platform enables the “ingestion” of multiple data analytics functions / tasks to enable the development of adaptive preventive and intervention models for different risks and contributing factors associated with Pancreatic Cancer. The **Analytic Workbench** component provides a complete information processing framework that will incorporate declarative methods for the specification of targeted analysis tasks, as well as declarative analytics to include predictive data services (especially from generic methods such as time series modelling).

The objectives of this component are:

- To define a workbench for analytic functions that can extract meaningful information from integrated big-datasets
- To facilitate scalable real-time big data management and analytics (including outcomes of analytics such as models) through an analytics workbench that supports processing across multiple data analytic functions

6.4.1.2 Interactions with other components

The analytic workbench facilitates openness and usability by allowing any actor (e.g., researcher, healthcare professional, data provider, etc.) to develop on-demand adaptive learning models for different risks based on the application of advanced AI analytic techniques.

The **Analytic Workbench** component uses the following sub-components to materialize the desired objectives:

- ICE AI & Analytics is the core backend platform for training, adjusting, packaging, and executing analytic models. It has been developed to extract value through the generation, training, and deployment of supervised and unsupervised analytic models. It allows the user for addressing their problem, so that he or she can select the most appropriate ML algorithm from the available families (such as Deep Learning Encoder, Clustering, Regression, Convolutional Networks, etc.). The model, once trained, will be deployed and executed in the iHelp environment.
- Advanced Analytics Workbench Notebook aims to bring the features via Jupyter Notebook open-source tool to address experienced Data Scientists that have deep knowledge in ML programming languages, such as Python or Scala, as a new module to ICE AI & Analytics.
- Apache Superset is an open-source software cloud-native application for data exploration and data visualization capable of handling data at petabyte scale (big data). Superset is used as a fast, lightweight and intuitive solution that makes it easy for users of all skill sets to explore and visualize their data, from simple line charts to highly detailed geospatial charts.
- Apache Kafka is a framework implementation of a software bus using stream-processing. Apache Kafka is used as a distributed event streaming platform that is used to support high-performance data pipelines, streaming analytics and data integrations.

Based on the interactions depicted in Figure 7, the Analytic Workbench will provide the necessary infrastructure (software libraries, scripts, and API REST) that allows the training, deployment, configuration and execution of analytic applications/services (related to risk identification, predictions, etc.) in the iHelp platform. In this respect, the users (i.e., developers of analytic services in the iHelp platform) will interact with the **Analytic Workbench** to train, deploy, configure and execute their services. To support the user engagement, the Analytic Workbench will provide an administrative dashboard interface that will also allow the monitoring of different analytic services that are using the workbench. It will also indirectly interact with the **Big Data Platform** in order to store the training models and allow the ML algorithms to consume and store healthcare records from the database.

6.4.2 Personalised Predictor

6.4.2.1 Objective of the software artefact

The **Personalised Predictor** is responsible to deliver the necessary toolset that enables the usage of advanced AI learning techniques towards the development of a personalized health model. This tool will assist in the identification of specific diseases, along with their contributing factors and it will support the scalability and security needs of personalized health data. For the implementation of the **Personalized Predictor**, various ML models of Deep Neural Networks will be trained, with the goal of modeling associations between the patient data and the available disease related data (e.g.: disease onset,

exacerbation, adverse effects of therapy, patient compliance, patient risky behaviours, patient lifestyle). Hidden patterns could be discovered and the extracted knowledge would help the study of the disease.

In terms of data, the **Personalised Predictor** component aims to analyze retrospective/historical clinical data in order to determine the significance of the predictor variables in relation to the risk of developing the PC disease or toxicity outcomes in case of already diagnosed patients.

6.4.2.2 Interactions with other components

The **Personalised Predictor** will use the HHR records stored in the iHelp repository in order to analyse the dataset and train the health models that will be developed in accordance with the user needs. The output will be the trained health models that will be used to identify associations and perform predictions about the disease. The **Personalised Predictor** will make use of the infrastructure provided by the **Analytics Workbench** in order to expose the predictive analytics functionality implemented in the trained ML models. The **Analytics Workbench** component acts as a wrapper of the REST API that the **Personalised Predictor** exposes for triggering either training of a model or inference about risk. Internally, the **Personalised Predictor** implements an asynchronous execution model by using task queues. Another integration point is through the **DSS Dashboard** so that the user that interact with the trained ML models to make inferences and inspect the results.

6.4.3 Predictor and Risk identifier

6.4.3.1 Objective of the software artefact

The goals of the **Predictor and Risk Identifier (PRI)** component are to predict Pancreatic Cancer risks in individuals, as well as perform assessment on the identified risks. The **PRI** component will develop feature extraction models in order to identify key attributes in the patients' health records and prediction models that will take into account the full range of attributes in the HHR records and the output of the feature extraction models, so that in the end it will identify the risks and their evolution in time.

The **PRI** component actually enhances the functionality provided by the **Personalised Predictor** in terms of involving data about a patient's life habit and investigates how the life habit trends affect the clinical risk factors in the development of the disease or the possible toxicity outcomes for patients already diagnosed with PC.

6.4.3.2 Interactions with other components

The **Predictor and Risk Identifier** uses the HHR records for its analysis and training of the necessary models. These operations can be triggered by an admin user or be schedule-based, considering that the HHR records will be enriched in the course of time. The **PRI** component also performs predictions and risk assessments, so an API will be provided for a user to enter the proper parameters and receive the relevant results, potentially through the **DSS Dashboard**. The REST API exposed by the **PRI** component will be wrapped in the **Analytical Workbench** in order to expose the functionality of the trained ML models.

6.4.4 Personalised Advisor

6.4.4.1 Objective of the software artefact

The **Personalised Advisor** module is a microservice that makes use of a small set of different microservices (i.e. a microservice cluster). The main objective of the **Personalised Advisor** module is to control the advice messages and dialogues that are presented to the end-users of the Mobile App (see §6.2.2). The component facilitates this in two different ways:

- Acting as a gateway service for other components to communicate to the mobile app.
- Acting as a smart component that makes decisions on when and what to say to the mobile app user.

6.4.4.2 Interactions with other components

In Figure 17 below we show the Personalised Advisor module and all related/surrounding components. The iHelp Personalised Advisor module is the core component here, that uses the various WOOL Services to send notifications/messages/dialogue to the Mobile App through the Virtual Coach Service. The three “cloud” modules depicted are:

- **iHelp Personalised Advisor** – the core microservice of the cluster – this component serves 2 main purposes (1) to pass-through recommendations/advice generated by other iHelp components to the Mobile App and end-user, and (2) to make decisions on which advice to provide to the user at which point in time.
- **T5.2 (“Design of Personalised Prevention and Intervention Measures”)** – Not an actual platform component but a relevant task in the project. T5.2 is the place where the content to be presented by the personalised advisor is being designed and authored.
- **WOOL Repository Service** – A service that stores WOOL Projects, containing collections of WOOL Dialogues, which are handcrafted scripted definitions of coaching dialogues (to be developed as iHelp service and released as an open-source WOOL module).
- **WOOL Variable Store Service** – A service that stores WOOL Variable values for specific end-users. WOOL Variables are simple, primitively typed variables that can be used within the definition of WOOL Dialogues (to be developed as iHelp service and released as open-source WOOL module).

Then, as stated in the objectives of this module, the Personalised Advisor communicates with the Healthentia Edge Component that is depicted by the following set of components:

- **Mobile App** – the main user interface for the primary end-users of the iHelp platform (patients or citizens) – see §6.2.2
- **Healthentia Web Portal** – a web-based user interface for clinicians, or other (healthcare) professionals that allows configuration of studies, managing users, viewing detailed data visualisations, and scheduling coaching actions to primary end-users.
- **Healthentia Data Service** – an internal back-end platform component dealing with capturing and providing access to measured data (e.g., sensor data, questionnaires, events, or log data). For additional details see §6.3.7 – Secondary Data Pre-processor.
- **Healthentia Virtual Coach Service** – an internal back-end platform component that controls the delivery of “coaching actions” (e.g., feedback messages, or dialogues) to users of the mobile application, and possibly professional users of the Web Portal.

These four components of the Healthentia Edge Component are depicted in Figure 7 (Overall Architecture) in the centre/bottom of the high-level architecture overview.

Figure 17: Personalised Advisor module and all related/surrounding components

Finally, Figure 17 shows, in the top right, one additional component:

- **WOOL Dialogue Editor** – A GUI Tool that allows non-technical domain experts to author coaching dialogues using the WOOL Dialogue language. A working version of the dialogue editor exists as open source, and improvements will be made to match the iHelp requirements (see §6.4.4.3).

The delivery of personalised healthcare and real-time feedback in iHelp is an interplay between the **Personalised Advisor** (a back-end service component) and the **Mobile App** (the main user interface component for the end-user). The Personalised Advisor is a smart service to be developed in the iHelp project, while the Mobile App will be based on the existing Healthentia Mobile application to be extended to support the various iHelp use cases.

When we are talking about personalised healthcare delivery, we are talking about three key concepts have to be considered: (1) visualising measured data, (2) providing simple feedback messages, and (3) engaging

the user in a dialogue with the digital virtual coach (see also D2.3 (“State of the art and requirements analysis III”). As such, these three coaching actions (“*show data visualisation*”, “*give feedback message*”, and “*trigger coaching dialogue*”) are the three possible outputs of the **Personalised Advisor** component. In short: the personalised advisor decides for every iHelp user *when* to deliver *which* one or more of the coaching actions.

The process of delivering such coaching actions is proposed to work in the following way. We explain the process step-by-step, following the encircled numbers in Figure 17.

1. A health expert authors a coaching dialogue using the WOOL Dialogue specification language, using the WOOL Dialogue Editor (a graphical user interface tool – Figure 18). In our example, the health expert authors an interactive dialogue that lets the user agree on a physical activity goal in cooperation with the iHelp virtual coach.
2. The health expert is logged in with their iHelp credentials, identifying them as the owner of a specific WOOL Project (e.g., related to Pilot #1). Logged in with the proper authentication, the health expert can store their WOOL dialogue in the WOOL Repository Service.
3. The WOOL Repository service contains a number of WOOL Projects (collections of WOOL dialogues), and knows which users have read/write access to those projects.
4. The iHelp Personalised Advisor can retrieve the latest set of WOOL Dialogues relevant to a specific pilot.
5. The Personalised Advisor makes a decision that a subject should set a physical activity coaching goal now.
6. The trigger to start the “physical_activity_goal” dialogue for the specified user as soon as possible (now), is sent to the Healthentia Edge Component.
7. The Healthentia Edge Component retrieves the latest Dialogue definition for the “physical_activity_goal” dialogue from the WOOL Repository Service.
8. The Healthentia Edge Component retrieves the latest set of WOOL Variables needed to execute the current dialogue (e.g., \$userAge, \$userGender, etc..).
9. The Healthentia Edge Component sends a trigger to execute this dialogue to the subject’s mobile application.
10. When the user sees the notification that the virtual coach has something to say, the mobile application will execute the dialogue – engaging with the user in the dialogue about physical activity goal setting.
11. When the dialogue is started (or finished), a notification of delivery is sent back to the Healthentia Edge Component.
12. The notification of delivery is passed back to the source of the coaching action trigger (i.e., the Personalised Advisor). In this case, the personalised advisor can know that its triggered advice has reached the end-user.

13. After the user has finished interacting with the dialogue, any updated or newly set WOOL Variables are passed back to the Healthentia Edge Component. In this example, the WOOL dialogue led to a new variable being set: \$userActivityGoal = 10000”.

14. The WOOL Variables that need updating are sent to the WOOL Variable Store Service for storage.

6.4.4.3 WOOL Dialogue Editor

WOOL is an Open Source (MIT Licensed) platform for authoring and executing scripted dialogues that was designed and developed specifically for the purpose of integrated personalized health coaching dialogue into eHealth applications. WOOL was developed in the context of a previous EU H2020 project called “Council of Coaches” and is currently maintained by partners of that project Roessingh Research and Development and Innovation Sprint. WOOL is and forever will be fully open source and has support for continuous development from various EU R&D projects for the coming years.⁴

The WOOL Platform will be used in iHelp to support advice delivery in the form of conversations between a virtual coach and the end-user. As part of the Personalised Advisor workflow, the WOOL Editor is the tool that allows professionals to design their own scripted dialogue (see Figure 18 below).

Figure 18: Screenshot of the WOOL Editor Tool, a work in progress GUI for authoring WOOL Dialogues.

The screenshot shows the structure of a collection of WOOL dialogues (left), and the main Dialogue Editing window on the right. Every box in the dialogue editor window is a step in the conversation, which are linked to other steps as shown by the arrows. The WOOL Editor will be updated to reflect the needs arising from the various iHelp use cases.

⁴ For more information see www.woolplatform.eu.

6.4.5 Monitoring and Alerting

6.4.5.1 Objective of the software artefact

The main goal of the **Monitoring and Alerting** module is to track and/or monitor the effect of the recommendations that are prescribed to the individuals by the clinician/medical experts. The module (and its sub-modules) will run as a separate service and will observe, check, and aggregate data coming from secondary data sources (mobile and/or wearable devices), and compare them with personalized targets issued by the clinicians/medical experts.

The monitoring mechanism will be executed on assigned configurable intervals (daily, weekly, monthly etc.), will make a quick assessment of progress towards goals, and will decide whether to activate the alerting submodule. The decisions will be based on comparing certain monitored parameter target values defined in the personalized advices against real values. Different escalation policies and threshold values will be considered when generating the proper alert and alert recipient (monitored individual or the advisor). The alerting functionality will be embedded in the delivery mechanism as part of mobile application.

For the second part of the project, it has been envisaged a new functionality of this module, aiming to evaluate the impact of the advice, sent to the citizens/patients, on their behaviour. The main goal should be to monitor and highlight to the clinicians how and if the specific advice changed the lifestyle of the recipients. For doing that, the citizens/patients will be clustered using common characteristics (e.g. age, gender, BMI if available) in order to compare the advice sent to a similar population. The result of this analysis could contribute to better fine tune the model for generating the advice and the user to be reached.

6.4.5.2 Interactions with other components

The **Monitoring and Alerting** module will be packed up in a docker image and deployed in a Kubernetes container/pod, thus being part of the iHelp platform. It will consume and store data into the **Big Data Platform**. The container will provide API endpoints for the monitoring and alerting functionalities but also a React-based application that will provide UI for the management of the recommendations for a given patient.

The React-based application will be utilized by the HCP to set specific target values for the rules in the selected from the UI mitigation plan (recommendations) and patient. In addition, the HCP will also be able to select a message template that will be used when an alert is generated. The Monitoring and Alerting module will aggregate data for the selected patient and this data will then be evaluated towards the target values of the mitigation plan. When an alert is generated according to the results of the evaluation, the message template will be used for the concrete message generation that will be sent to the user.

The React-based application will be integrated into the **DSS platform** from where the HCP will be able to access the UI and manage the recommendations.

The Monitoring and Alerting module can be started on certain configurable intervals and work with respect to the FaaS (*Function-as-a-Service*) paradigm or it can run continuously depending on the level of granularity of achieving the targets, set by the advices, we want to track, the time of reaction and the most appropriate thresholds and value tolerances we have set.

The **Monitoring and Alerting** module will use the following simple logic:

1. The service will be started [on certain configurable intervals];
2. It will obtain a list of currently active personal advice.;
3. In the context of each rule: aggregate row data if rule uses comparison of aggregated data against target;
4. It will obtain a list of aggregated data regarding the individuals from the advices;
5. It will evaluate actual values vs targets;
6. Based on various parameters to be monitored, (target value, escalation policy, etc.) the system will generate alerts, to be sent to the individual or the clinician;
7. Generated alerts are sent to the appropriate person using the delivery mechanism, as for instance directly to the **Personalised Advisor** towards the mobile app or **DSS Dashboard** waiting for the HCP approval then through the **Personalized Advisor** for further distribution to the user.

In order to work properly, the module requires the following interfaces:

- Raw data for evaluation – we need an interface that will provide specified data type for a given individual in a given period
- Personalised advices – (individual, alert title and content, parameters to be monitored , target value, escalation policy) from personal adviser will be obtained on certain intervals (daily, weekly, or predefined target date)
- Strategy list – obtain a list of strategies defining what actions should be performed if certain target values have been reached – e.g. notify user twice, if still in warning notify clinician, escalate one week later. Strategies to be supported should be aligned with pilots and provided as explicit requirements
- Alert distribution / delivery – mechanism to send certain alert to certain individual (achieved through the Personalized Advisor delivery mechanism or invoke virtual coach, see §6.4.4).

The **Monitor and Alerting** module will offer the following interfaces:

- **Data Aggregator** – if required – aggregate raw data for a period – how many steps user has done in a week
- **Alert Evaluation** – do we have a match between certain advice target and user results
- **Alert Generator** – replace placeholders in advice with actual values and send them to alert distribution interface according to strategy and personal preferences
- **Rules management** – UI that provides the ability to create, edit, list and manage monitoring, alerting and feedback rules

6.5 Data storage

6.5.1 Big Data Platform

6.5.1.1 Objective of the software artefact

This software artefact provides the persistent data management layer of the iHelp platform. It will rely on LXS data store and its main objectives are the following:

- **To allow for data ingestion at very high rates.** Based on its internal ultra-scalable transactional engine of LXS and the sophisticated internal data structures for data indexing, the Big Data Platform can allow for highly rated data ingestion, avoiding the high contention of traditional relational data stores, and providing transactional semantics that the NoSQL world sacrifices for the sake of scalability. This will be used in the data ingestion pipelines that will be established for migrating data into the iHelp platform, either by batch ingestion (periodic or static), or by sending data over a stream. Having that, batch ingestion of a high volume of data can finish in the order of magnitude of minutes rather than hours, thus making the data ingestion process very efficient.
- **To allow for efficient query execution for analytical processing over the operational data.** The Big Data Platform provides Hybrid Transactional and Analytical Processing (HTAP) that allows to perform analytics over the operation data, as data is being ingested, without the need for migrating historical data into a data warehouse and perform the analytic operations there. This means that the analytics will always access fresh and not obsolete data and can provide insights over the real data set. By providing the rich query processing capabilities of the relational data stores, data pre-processing can be efficiently executed near the data storage, avoiding the need to send the entire datasets to the analytical processing layer, while the intra-operation parallelism of the query engine allows for parallel execution of analytical and aggregated operations.
- **To allow for federated query processing, combining data that are stored externally to the Big Data Platform.** Using the polyglot capabilities of its query engine, the Big Data Platform can open connections and push down queries to be processed in other instances that might be deployed externally. This can be the case where each organization has deployed its own instance of the iHelp platform, and might need to correlate data that are stored internally, with data that are stored in another organization. The **Big Data Platform** can accept such queries over federated data stores, open connections to the external ones to access data, push the query execution there, retrieve only result of such execution (without having to move data between the different instances) and combine those with the data stored internally.

6.5.1.2 Interactions with other components

The **Big Data Platform** is a central component of the iHelp platform and it interacts with almost all other software artefacts of the platform. It will be provided as an internal component with a static deployment, with scaling capabilities at runtime in order to cope with increased workloads. This component is mainly used for others to read or to store data and it will only read data autonomously in case of a federated query execution via its polyglot engine. We categorize its interactions with the other components in two different types: One used for storing data and one used for reading data.

Inserts:

The main software artefact that will interact with the **Big Data Platform** in order to store data is the HHR Importer. The latter will communicate with the Big Data Platform either by its standard JDBC connectivity mechanism, or by making use of its dual SQL/NoSQL interface and its direct API that allows data arrived in a Kafka data queue to be ingested at very high rates. Another option that can be investigated in a latter phase of the project, is the communication of the HHR Importer with the **Big Data Platform**, via an intermediate Kafka data queue. In such a case, the LXS Kafka connector will be used, which inserts data transparently to the datastore. In this case, the **HHR Importer** will have to serialize the data to be ingested via an Avro schema registry.

Another category of software artefact that needs to interact with the **Big Data Platform** to insert data are the analytical functions that will need to persistently store intermediate or final results, or even store the training results of their algorithms. They will either communicate directly using the standard JDBC data connectivity mechanism of the datastore, or via the Analytic Workbench via Kafka data queues using the same mechanism explained before.

Reads:

The first category of software artefacts that need to interact with the **Big Data Platform** in order to perform read operations will be the analytical functions. Those functions need to read raw data stored in the data repository in the common data model coming from either primary or secondary resources. They will either make use of the standard JDBC data connectivity mechanism of the datastore, or they can also rely on their own analytical frameworks to perform the pre-processing for their analysis. In case they make use of the Spark analytical framework, then they can also benefit from the LXS Spark connector.

A second category of software artefacts includes the ones that are being involved in the data ingestion process. In some cases where it's envisioned that some of the intermediate functions of the data ingestion pipeline might need to read historical data to perform some analysis. They can also make use of the JDBC data connection mechanism of the **Big Data Platform**, or any of the provisioned means for data connectivity, including the spark connector.

Finally, this component will interact with the visual analytic tools in order to visualize the result of the analysis. Once again, the most appropriate way is to make use of the JDBC standard connectivity mechanism of the datastore, or if this is not possible, via REST endpoints. Regarding the latter case, there are two means for interacting with the **Big Data Platform** through REST. The first is to rely on the datastore's built-in support for Odata⁵ of the datastore. This is an OASIS standard for interacting with a data source using REST calls and has been already implemented by the Big Data Platform. It can be considered as a built-in functionality inside the virtualized container where the datastore is deployed. However, there might be cases where the Odata implementation does not cover the needs of the visual analytic tools or its performance is not efficient when processing relatively big amount of data volume. For that, the communication will be done via the iHelp Store REST component which was designed to solve specific needs of the DSS and visual analytic tools.

⁵ <https://www.odata.org/>

6.5.2 iHelp Store Rest

6.5.2.1 Objective of the software artefact

The **iHelp Store Rest** serves the need to interact with the **Big Data Platform** via a REST interface, in cases the already provided Odata connectivity does not cover the needs of the data clients. As it has been mentioned in the previous subsection, the Big Data Platform provides a variety of different means for data connectivity. However, the majority of those is relevant for backend core components or AI algorithms that needs to interact with the database. However, frontend and UI components are usually implemented using technologies that cannot or should not interact directly with the datastore. For these cases, a REST API should be offered that allows the frontend components to consume data through it. For these cases, the **Big Data Platform** has its Odata implementation to provide this layer, but during the second year of the project, we identified that this is not enough.

Due to this, in this second version of the architecture, we introduced a new component, the *iHelp Store Rest*, that implements specific functionality to be used by the UI components, and more precisely, the **DSS Dashboard**. The latter allows the end-user to navigate through the raw data stored in the database in the HHR relational model and interact with it by consuming and combining data from different entities or data tables. Odata already provides this, but comes with certain constraints. The **iHelp Store Rest** allows the **DSS Dashboard** to retrieve meta-information of the data schema, like table names and columns, relations between tables (i.e. foreign key relationships) and other statistic information like histograms, etc. Moreover, in contrast with the Odata that allows retrieving data only from specific tables (or expanding their results exploiting foreign keys using their *navigation* properties), the *iHelp Store Rest*, allows its clients to submit more sophisticated query statements for data retrieval, exploiting all capabilities of the relational algebra. Therefore, the end-user can get information about the underlying data schema, and, combining this information, is capable to define complicated queries including *join* operators, or *aggregations*. Last but not least, the **iHelp Store Rest** is capable to choose either the direct API of the **Big Data Platform** to retrieve data in a more efficient manner, or its relational query engine, in case the query statement involves operations that are not supported by the storage engine (i.e. in case of *joining* data tables).

The **iHelp Store Rest** will be deployed as a standalone java process that offers the microservice implementing its functionality. Internally, it contains an embedded servlet container that allow the interaction with its clients using http/https, as the REST protocol demands.

6.5.2.2 Interactions with other components

The **iHelp Store Rest** can interact with all components that belong to the GUI category. At this phase of the project, it will be is mainly consumed by the **DSS Dashboard** that initially created the need of such functionality. However, it can extend its functionalities, implementing additional REST APIs that might be needed by other components of the GUI category. On the other hand, it establishes data connection with the **Big Data Platform**, either using the JDBC driver or the direct API of the latter. It is very important to highlight that this component only retrieves data from the datastore, thus allowing only for read operations. Data modification operators must be submitted by the core components of the iHelp platform, thus the HHR importer and the AI algorithms via the **Analytical Workbench**.

7 Infrastructure

In the context of the iHelp project, UPRC will provide the needed computing and storage capabilities to set-up the cloud-based infrastructure to serve the project needs and in order for all the needed technologies and tools to be deployed and managed by project's partners. Overall, this cloud infrastructure aims to help data scientists, healthcare professionals and different stakeholders, to analyse a wide plethora of datasets from different data sources, and facilitate the study of the clinical, physiological, personal and societal aspect of Pancreatic Cancer conditions and treatments.

Furthermore, the project's Consortium has identified a list of needed tools that must be provided and be available to all partners in terms of the overall proposed architecture and the integration and deployment/management of their solutions/components. On top of this, the CI/CD approach represented below, that should be followed during the whole lifecycle of iHelp project and the corresponding technologies/tools have been identified and are shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Identified tools

Moreover, the provided infrastructure will help project's partners to run computation- or data- intensive tasks and host online services in virtual machines or using virtualized containers on the provisioned IT resources. To facilitate the cloud provisioning of resources for the project and to collect all the technical needs, UPRC has invited project members to report technical needs in a shared document. A document listing partners' technical needs, which was introduced during one of the iHelp consortium meetings organized by the Project Coordinator was set up, is a live document, and is attached in the Annex A - Infrastructure Discussion.

The aforementioned document is composed of two main sections. In Section 2 (Technical Groups), are listed the appropriate technical partners have been indicated, who will be responsible for the above presented tools/technologies of the CI/CD approach. Different technical groups of partners have been organised based on their expertise, experience, and level of familiarity with these technologies/tools, in order to discuss activities, approaches, and guidelines and to drive the deployment and maintenance of these technologies/tools. The latter is being facilitated based on the role assignment shown in Table 7 (see Appendix), where specific (groups of) partners will be now responsible for providing, deploying, and maintaining the corresponding technologies/tools. Moreover, in this specific table the needed resources for each tool are currently recorded in order everyone to be aware of the needs and the overall architecture that will be followed. On top of this, in Section 3 of this shared document (Infrastructure Resources) Table 8 is made available allowing reports needs of each partner to provide their needs on Infrastructure Resources for components and tools deployment.

The envisaged infrastructure is provided for the technical partners as a testing environment, accessible remotely and in which every component leader is responsible to test the component and the integration with the other software artefacts present on the platform.

An identical infrastructure will be provided for the validation of the solution. On this instance all the components will be deployed, and the pilots will validate the actual operation of the whole platform.

It is important to note that both the testing and the validation infrastructure will not handle real data, but a set of synthetic data (M., M. 21) useful only for testing and validation phases.

The pilots, on their premises, will have to provide the defined infrastructure in order to allow the deployment of the needed iHelp components, otherwise, if needed, they could use the centralised solution, adopting the Software as a Service approach. In this later case, nothing will be deployed on their premises.

7.1 Guidelines for the integration workflow

Currently, we have deployed Gitlab on top of the provisioned infrastructure, using a virtual machine of 8 virtual cores with 8 GB of memory and 40GB of disk and 300GB of block storage. Gitlab allows for the software providers to upload their source code or precompiled libraries/packages that will be needed to create dockerized images. As a matter, the software providers have two options: i) use gitlab defined CI to evaluate the source code using the SonarQubes and compile the source code to software artifacts or ii) ensure code quality externally on their premises and directly upload the precompiled libraries or packages to the gitlab. The second option allows for partners that provide proprietary technology to make it available to the consortium without revealing the details of the code.

In either case, each software provider needs to define the *Dockerfile* that will allow the CI process to automatically build the dockerized image that will be needed during the deployment/delivery phase. The software providers are eligible to either rely on the automated process for generating those images using the CI pipelines defined in Gitlab, or to manually create the images and push them to the private docker registry of the project, provided by our Gitlab installation. At the end, either manually or triggered by the CI pipelines, the docker images for each of the provided components of iHelp is now available there.

Having the images now created, the next step was for the responsible partner to install and configure the Kubernetes cluster for the components to be deployed on top. Currently, at this phase of the project we have a virtual machine of 8 cores 16GB of memory, 40GB of disk and 300GB of block storage to host the *master* node of the Kubernetes cluster, with 2 virtual machines of 8 virtual cores and 8GB of memory each for the *worker* nodes to make use of. These resources will be scaled out at the later phases of the project in order to cover future needs as more and more AI algorithms and software components will be delivered. Scaling out the cluster is feasible by creating additional virtual machines (preferable of the same size) and install additional *worker nodes* on top of each of those.

The use of a Kubernetes cluster to deploy all technology building blocks introduces the necessity for all components to be compliant with such deployments. This is facilitated by the fact that all of them are delivered via docker images that can be injected with configuration parameters during the deployment/instantiation phase. This requires Kubernetes manifests to be provided by each software component so that the system administrator can make use of them. In those cases when a building block is composed by different internal component, using the *docker-compose* to deploy the overall solution, a specialized task force has been defined in the consortium that translates the docker-compose file to Kubernetes manifest.

As it has been already mentioned, different pilots have different restrictions, with the most common one to be related with GDPR and data privacy constraints. Due to this, it might be impossible to make use of a public available installation to process that sensitive information. For such cases, the deployment will take place on premise using the pilot specific infrastructure. However, we will still rely on our common testbed and infrastructure provided by the UPRC for validating the integration of the components. Due to this, we are currently defining the CD pipelines to be used for the continuous delivery of the iHelp platform. Using those pipelines each time a new update is being pushed to Gitlab, either triggering the automated CI pipelines to build the docker image or manually by the responsible software provider, the CD corresponding pipeline for the component will be triggered afterwards. This will target the infrastructure provided by the consortium where the Kubernetes cluster has been configured. Due to this, it is mandatory for all software components to provide their corresponding Kubernetes manifest to allow such a deployment. The common testbed can be used for testing purposes and validating the overall solution before the actual deployment in each pilot takes place. The common testbed will only store sample and synthetic data used only for the validation of the overall integrated functionality. However, exploiting the virtualization of the deployment, it is feasible to copy the overall integrated solution to the pilot's target infrastructure on their premises, allowing them now to consume their real data using iHelp tools and AI algorithms.

Last but not least, it is important to make a distinction between static (always present) and dynamic (on demand) components. The first category is related with the components that formulates the core of the iHelp platform. That is the **Big Data Platform** with its **iHelp Store Rest**, the **Data Gateway**,

the **Analytical Workbench**, the **DSS Dashboard** etc. On the second category lie the components that will be instantiated and run on demand, but there is no need for them to be running all the time. In this category lie the components that are responsible to execute the AI algorithms offered by the platform. These algorithms are executed via the **Analytic Workbench**. The latter makes use of the underlying Kubernetes cluster for the provision of the virtualized resources and makes use of the docker images of the AI components to create the corresponding containers, upon demand. Their lifecycle ends when the AI algorithm return the result to be stored to the Big Data Platform, and then the container is deleted by the Analytical Workbench, in order to release resources. That way, the consumption of the overall resources is much more efficient as we do not require for computational power for each of the available AI algorithms, rather than only for the ones that are currently doing some work.

Table 5 in the next section summarises part of the live document aforementioned, in which the partners collected the hardware infrastructure requirements for their own components.

8 Deployment

In this section a description is given of what components (§6) will be deployed on which nodes of the infrastructure (§7).

Due to some ethical and legal aspects, it could be possible that in some cases data to be ingested cannot be shared and transferred across the countries. Another aspect to take in account is that not all the pilots have the same goal or expressed the same use cases, hence not all pilots will need the same iHelp features.

To overcome the former limitation and addressing the latter need, iHelp proposes for the first deployment, a modular, static and tailored deploy on the hospital premises. As an overview, each pilot holds its own raw data, and can use iHelp on the ingested data compliant to the common HHR data model

In case it becomes possible to transfer the data, and to use the platform as SaaS, the designed architecture could be deployed in a remote cloud and be accessed from the final users.

To determine the needed components for each partner, will be created several traceability matrices: the following, Table 1, regards the mapping between the pilots' requirement and the use cases.

The single use case encompasses more than one requirements, and its flow involves several components in order to satisfy the original requirements (present in D2.3)

Table 1: Traceability matrix (Requirements/UseCases)

ID	Develop Risk Prediction Model	Risk Assessment	Request Tests and Samples	Elevated Risk Detected	Ingest Tests and Samples results	Risk Mitigation – Treatment planning	Advice Review	Risk Mitigation Delivery	Monitoring	Advice Follow-up	Caption of profiling characteristics	Data Visualisation	Communication of risk	Social Network data extraction	Patient enrolment using DSS Dashboard	Patient enrolment using Heathentia
REQ-P1-01					x											
REQ-P1-02											x					
REQ-P1-03	x	x	x													
REQ-P1-04								x		x			x			
REQ-P1-05						x		x								
REQ-P1-06		x														
REQ-P2-01											x					
REQ-P2-02											x					
REQ-P2-03						x	x			x						
REQ-P2-04					x						x	x				
REQ-P2-05	x		x	x					x			x				
REQ-P3-01					x							x				
REQ-P3-02					x							x				
REQ-P3-03									x		x	x				
REQ-P3-04									x		x					
REQ-P3-05	x											x				
REQ-P3-06															x	x
REQ-P4-01	x											x				
REQ-P4-02	x											x				
REQ-P4-03	x				x							x				
REQ-P4-04	x										x	x				
REQ-P4-05							x	x		x						
REQ-P4-06		x		x								x				
REQ-P5-01					x						x			x		
REQ-P5-02											x					
REQ-P5-03						x		x					x			
REQ-P5-04								x								
REQ-P5-05	x				x							x				
REQ-P5-06					x											

REQ-P5-07					x							x				
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Table 2: Traceability matrix (Use Cases/Components)

	Required by:	HHR Importer	Data Gateway	Data Harmoniser	Data Cleaner	Data Qualifier	Data Connectors	Analytic Workbench	DSS Dashboard	Big Data Platform	Personalised Predictor	Predictor and Risk Identifier	Mobile App	Personalised Advisor	Social Analyser	Monitoring and Alerting	Secondary Data Pre-processor	iHelp Store Rest
Develop Risk Prediction Model	UNIMAN, HDM, MUP, TMU							x		?								x
Risk Assessment	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU							x	x	x	?	?						x
Request Tests and Samples	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU	?	?	?	?	?	?		x	?				?		?		x
Elevated Risk Detected	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU							x	x		?	?						
Ingest Tests and Samples results	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU	x	x	x	x	x	x			x								
Risk Mitigation/Treatment planning	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU	?	?	?	?	?	?		x	?								x
Advice Review	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU								x									
Risk Mitigation Delivery	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU												x	x				
Monitoring	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU	?	?	?	?	?	?			x			x	x		x	x	
Advice Follow-up	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU								x									
Caption of profiling characteristics	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU	x	x	x	x	x	x			x			x				x	
Plan a visit or control	FPG								x	x			x	x				x
Data Visualisation	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU								x	x								x

Required by:	HHR Importer	Data Gateway	Data Harmoniser	Data Cleaner	Data Qualifier	Data Connectors	Analytic Workbench	DSS Dashboard	Big Data Platform	Personalised Predictor	Predictor and Risk Identifier	Mobile App	Personalised Advisor	Social Analyser	Monitoring and Alerting	Secondary Data Pre-processor	iHelp Store Rest
Communication of risk	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU							X					X				
Social Network data extraction	TMU	?	?	?	?	?	?							X			
Patient enrolment using DSS Dashboard	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP							X									
Patient enrolment using Heathentia	HDM, TMU							X									

Table 2 shows a traceability matrix that has as main goal to summarise the impact of each use case, collected and available in the D2.3 (“State of the art and requirements analysis III”) (M., A., C., + 22), on the main components defined in this document.

For each use case, the components required for the standard flow are marked with a **x**, and with a **?** the components possibly involved by optional flows.

The specific flow and invocations will be better detailed in the scope of the task T2.3 (“Functional and Non-Functional Specification”).

Table 3: Traceability matrix (Pilots/Components)

	HHR Importer	Data Gateway	Data Harmoniser	Data Cleaner	Data Qualifier	Data Connectors	Analytic Workbench	DSS Dashboard	Big Data Platform	Personalised Predictor	Predictor and Risk identifier	Mobile App	Personalised Advisor	Social Analyser	Monitoring and Alerting	Secondary Data Pre-processor	WebApp for HCP
UNIMAN	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•
FPG	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•
HDM	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•
MUP	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
TMU	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•

Table 4: Pilots' needs regarding platform installation

	On-premises	SaaS
UNIMAN	•	
FPG	•	
HDM		•
MUP	•	
TMU	•	

Table 5: Hardware requirements per software artefact

Name	VCores [#]	RAM [GB]	Storage [GB]	GPU	Deployed externally	Included in requirements of:
HHR Importer	0	0,0 GB	0,0 GB			Data Capture Gateway
Data Gateway	2	1,0 GB	0,0 GB			
Data Harmoniser	8	32,0 GB	50,0 GB			

Name	VCores [#]	RAM [GB]	Storage [GB]	GPU	Deployed externally	Included in requirements of:
Data Cleaner						
Data Qualifier						
Data Capture Gateway	1	0,5 GB				
Analytic Workbench	16	32,0 GB	328,0 GB			
DSS Dashboard	4	8,0 GB	10,0 GB			
Big Data Platform	2	4,0 GB				
Personalised Predictor	0	0,0 GB	0,0 GB			Analytic Workbench
Predictor and Risk identifier	0	0,0 GB	0,0 GB			Analytic Workbench
Mobile App					x	
Personalised Advisor					x	
Social Analyser	6	16,0 GB	128,0 GB			
Monitoring and Alerting	1	4,0 GB	1,0 GB			
Secondary Data Pre-processor					x	
iHelp Store Rest	1	0,5 GB				
Keycloak	1	0,5 GB	1,0 GB			
Kubernetes	1	0,5 GB				
Kafka	2	4,0 GB				
Analytic Workbench: ML lifecycle + Jupiter	8	16,0 GB	128,0 GB			

Table 3 shows the functional dependencies of each use case, and related components, specified per pilot. That matrix, in this final version, can drive the deployment process in the next phases of the project. In that table, are summarised the needed components for each pilot. For every pilot a • means that the component in that column is needed and mandatory because it is present in the pilot functional requirements (D2.3).

Due to the modular approach, iHelp will be able to customise the final solution to only the needed components, do to optimise the actual resources. In Figure 20 and Figure 21 show two possible on-premises deployments, the first one with all the identified components, the second with a reduced number of deployed components.

During the period between the first and second version of this deliverable, the continuous analysis of pilot requirements and the dependencies of the software artefacts brought the result of the full deployment for on all the sites; but in any case, the deployment could be customised later on after the release of this document.

After the final phase of requirements refinement, the result is that four on out of five pilots need the iHelp platform installed on their premises, due to the Ethical Committee constraints and their internal privacy policy; this is summarised in Table 4.

Due to those needs, to the pilots' functional requirements, and to the features provided by the software components, the iHelp platform will be almost fully deployed on each of the pilots sites. The only optional component, that is requested for just one pilot (see D2.3), is the **Social Analyser**. Actually, also other pilots are expressing their will also to use such a tool, so the final decision about the deployment of that component will be delayed and in charge of the pilot site.

Table 5 summarizes the hardware minimum requirements needed by the software artefact to run smoothly. Those resources will be provided by each healthcare organization, in case of on-premises installation, and by the iHelp consortium, in case of SaaS installation.

As mentioned in section 7, the test and validation phases need the deployment of the whole set of features offered by iHelp, following that, Figure 20 can also represent the deployment diagram for the testing and validation phases, with the only exception of that the *device* in which is available the VM is not on the hospital premises, but on the iHelp centralised server.

As listed in section 7, all the backend components are containerised, so they need an execution environment, like Kubernetes, to be operative.

A different approach was adopted for the **AnalyticWorkbench**. It uses a container orchestration platform, developed by ICE and known as DryICE (Information Catalyst 22. It provides a data processing pipeline and CEP capabilities.

The consortium agreed for the first release of the platform, to perform a tailored, customized, static deployment of the services and functions involved in the data ingestion data pipeline. Once validated the features of the system and satisfied the pilots' requirements, the technical partners will investigate the possibility to have a "serverless" (B., C., C., + 17) deployment of such components. That approach will allow to dynamically instantiate the needed component only on demand. This approach could be useful in case of components invoked very rarely, that can be suspended for saving resources, and only if needed,

instantiated, and invoked. This approach, and the DryICE solution, will be better detailed in the WP4, and could impact some components developed in the scope of the WP3.

Another special mention in the deployment diagram is reserved to the **BigDataPlatform**. This software artefact, as already explained in §6.5.1, and further detailed in the related deliverable D4.9 (“Big data platform and knowledge management system I”) (K., M., P., + 21), can provide polyglot capabilities built in its query engine. This capability allows the final user (e.g.: a **ModelBuilder**) of the Pilot A to correlate some data, among a federated network of datastores, with a selection of data from Pilot B. In this example, we are assuming that both the pilots, i.e. A and B, have the **BigDataPlatform** deployed on their premises, and they established a federated datastore. The power of this feature is that the AI component does not have to know the infrastructural or network detail of the iHelp platform, but everything is delegated to the **BigDataPlatform**, invoked using the JDBC API in the same execution environment. It can be also used in scenarios when pilot A should make use of data coming from pilot B, but this data cannot live the premises of pilot B. As the **BigDataPlatform** can access the data remotely, there is no need to move this data from pilot B to be stored in the infrastructure of pilot A, rather than only retrieving the result of the pre-processing that will take place in pilot B, so that the data cannot move .

Figure 20: Deployment diagram - whole solution

Figure 21: Possible partial deployment

9 Conclusions

This document provides the view of the conceptual overall architecture and model of the iHelp platform. It highlights the main components, their interconnections, key capabilities and offered some details about the infrastructure and the approach that will be followed for the deployment of the platform.

All the details, and the internal design of each component, are demanded to the related tasks; in this document, instead, there is the higher-level image, and how the iHelp solution will be provided to the final users.

During this period the consortium agreed on some decisions regarding the architecture, most important, the software will be provided in form of containerised microservices; some of those will use an asynchronous communication (i.e. Data Ingestion), some others will use the synchronous communication (i.e. Data analysis). The connection with the iHelp repository will be performed using the various data connectivity mechanisms, some of which follow well-known standards, like the JDBC.

Three kinds of GUI will be provided to the application reserved to the clinicians; specifically, a GUI for the **HCP** for looking at the specific patient's data, a GUI for the **ModelBuilder**, that can allow to train and tune the AI algorithm implemented in the platform, a GUI for the **Policy Maker** to extract data from social network for fine tuning the policies in force.

The **Individual**, will interact with the system using only a mobile application, which can act as an aggregator of the user data that will be shared within iHelp.

The **Admin**, on the other hand, can have access to several components using the user interface, graphical or programmatically, provided directly by the specific software artefact.

Moreover, a centralised infrastructure will be provided, which can receive the deployment of all the components for testing and validation phases. This infrastructure will not handle real data, but only synthetic data. The minimum set of resources needed by the components, that will be provided by the infrastructure, is still in definition progress, the snapshot of the live document on which the technical partners are working on is in the annex.

The deployment, for the first phase, will be static for many of the identified components, but customised on the needs of the pilot, for a more efficient resources allocation.

The *serverless* deployment approach will be better analysed to understand if, for the specific pilots' scenarios, it could be feasible and efficient, for the second part of the project, to move some components toward such kind of development. The discussion within the Consortium on the infrastructure will continue out of the scope of this document. However, the basic concepts and decisions that have been documented here allow for the deployment of the components as *functions* into a *serverless* platform.

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List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CA	Consortium Agreement
CD	Continuous Delivery
CEP	Complex event processing
CI	Continuous Integration
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EEA	European Economic Area
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HCP	Health Care Professional
HHR	Holistic Health Records
K8S	Kubernetes
M	Month
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PC	Pancreatic Cancer
RAM	Random Access Memory
REST	Representational state transfer
SaaS	Software As A Service
SNA	Sentiment Network Analysis
T	Task
UC	Use Case
UML	Unified Modelling Language
VCore	Virtual Core
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package

Annex A - Infrastructure Discussion

Infrastructure & Architecture Discussions

As discussed and agreed during the 2nd & 3rd Virtual Consortium Meeting call of iHelp project, UPRC will provide the server and appropriate infrastructures in order all the needed technologies and tools to be able to be deployed and be managed by partners. UPRC can provide the wanted VMs for the project.

A set of tools was discussed agreed that need to be provided and be available to all partners in plans for the of integration and deployment/management of their solutions/components. On top of this, the below CI/CD approach that can be followed during the whole lifecycle of iHelp project, and the corresponding technologies/tools were proposed by Usman (ICE) during the 2nd Virtual Meeting Call of the iHelp Project.

Gitlab CI/CD

Partners develop locally and push tested version to the project Gitlab. Commits are tagged for deployment/publishing

- **Gitlab** → Code management and code hosting

Automatic code quality check is performed constantly by SonarQube

- **SonarQube** → Code quality review

Docker image specification is generated and image is created – this can be multiple files

- **Central Gitlab Docker Registry** → Hosting Docker image

Docker Compose and Helm Chart Registry for different components is created by the component providers

- **Docker Compose/Helm Chart Registry** → How you run Docker containers

Kubernetes will use the Helm Chart to build the integrated platform – using the set of available containers

- **Kubernetes** → Runtime environment for Docker containers

The set of containers, running in Kubernetes, can be managed through Rancher

- **Rancher** → Cluster management for Kubernetes

Runtime communication between different components is managed through a central Message Broker

- **Message Broker (e.g. Kafka)** → Run-time communication between different components

The below table summarises and indicates the Open Issues and Discussions that have been raised according to Architecture and Infrastructures during our latest Virtual Meeting still open at the time of writing the current deliverable.

Table 6: Infrastructural open points

Open Discussion Items	Description	Technical Partners Involved
Use of a container-orchestration system	<p>UPRC can provide VMs over OpenStack using their infrastructure. It is recommended the use of a container-orchestrator system (i.e. Kubernetes) so that everything can be easy deployed when needed.</p> <p>The latter will require:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. All platform components/tools to be containerized. 2. Native and locally deployed applications, also from pilotσ, might need to be containerized (that might require the help of a technical partners) but there 	All

	might be always the option for them to deploy in a separate VM.	
Use of a Serverless vs a Static Microservices Deployment	Most of the technical partners raised the issue of having a serverless deployment and utilization of our microservices, in order to trigger and utilize these microservices dynamically. Maybe we have scenarios which do not need all functions/microservices to be utilized, thus it is proposed to have a more dynamic deployment. - During the 3 rd Consortium Meeting it was proposed from Pavlos (LXS) & Sakis (ATC) for the WP3 components to have static deployments at least until the 1 st Review. It is strongly recommended to have our deployments on top of Kubernetes. Hence, there is no need for extra VM for each component. WP4 components will be based on serverless implementation based on DryICE tool provided from ICE.	WP3 components static implementation, WP4 components serverless implementation based on DryICE.
(Any other discussion that should be raised)		

Technical Groups

Appropriate technical partners should be named/indicated, who will be responsible for the above presented tools/technologies of the CI/CD approach. Different technical groups of partners should be organised based on their expertise, experience, and level of familiarity with these technologies/tools, in order to discuss activities, approaches, and guidelines and to drive the deployment and maintenance of these technologies/tools. The latter will be facilitated based on the below table, where specific (group of) partners will be responsible for providing, deploying, and maintaining the corresponding technologies/tools. Moreover, in the below table the needed resources for each technology/tool to be deployed should be recorded in order everyone to be aware of the needs and the overall architecture that will be followed.

For example, Kafka must be deployed on a project's single VM with a Public IP in order every partner to be aware and able to connect, produce and consume messages from the appropriate Kafka Topics under this specific IP. For this deployment, a VM of 4vcores, 8GB RAM and 50GB storage is needed.

Table 7: Infrastructural tools

Technology/Tool	Description	Responsible Partner(s)	Needed Resources
Gitlab	The project's private GitLab repository, so that everyone be able to push and share code. Each organization must have at least one account with admin/maintenance rights, so that people can administer the components that their organization is responsible for.	UPRC	1 VM with 8 vcores, 32GB RAM, 1 Public IP and 100GB storage.

	Each member of the consortium should have one account there.		
Central Gitlab Container Registry	Gitlab container registry, so that it is feasible to build, upload and store Docker Images in project's own and private repo. Docker images will be later used by Kubernetes to create the containers and orchestrate the overall deployment.	UPRC	Deployed on top of Gitlab, thus no extra resources are needed.
SonarQube	Automatic code quality check is performed constantly by this tool.	ICE	Deployed on top of Kubernetes, yml file. Specify in the pipelines through the Gitlab pipelines. Components have to have their own libraries. E.g. Jacoco for Java.
Kubernetes	Kubernetes will be utilized for the orchestration of the deployments of the containerized components.	ICE	TBD. Minimum requirements. 2 Kubernetes instances were proposed during the 3 rd Consortium Meeting.
Docker Compose/Helm Chart registry	Will be used for defining and running multi-container Docker applications.	UPRC	Deployed on top of Docker. In general docker compose can easily be transposed to Kubernetes docker.
Rancher	Cluster Manager for Kubernetes	ICE	Deployed on top of Kubernetes
Kafka	The Message Bus/Broker of the project. Run time communication between different components of the overall pipeline.	LXS	Will be deployed on top of Kubernetes. Needed resources should be calculated along with Kubernetes resources.
Serverless Orchestrator (e.g. DryICE)		ICE	TDB
(Any other tool that should be highlighted)			

Infrastructure Resources

Based on the below table each partner can provide his needs on Infrastructure Resources, in order to deploy his own components and tools.

Table 8: Infrastructural resources

Partner	Description of Actions	Needed Resources
UPRC	T3.4 Standardization and Quality Assurance of Heterogeneous Data	1VM with 8vcores, 32GB RAM, 50GB storage
LXS	Kafka on top of Kubernetes	2vcores 4GB RAM
LXS	Datastore	2vcores 4GB RAM
LXS	Data Capture	1core, 512MB RAM
LXS	REST on top of Datastore	1core, 512MB RAM
ICE	T4.2 Analytic Workbench (DryICE)	TBD. Minimum resources needed.
UPM	T4.3 DSS	4core, 4- 8GB RAM, 10GB storage
ATC	T4.1, T5.1 predictors	vCPU: 16 cores, RAM: 32Gb
(Please all partners fill up the table according to your needs.)		